

Generalized Analysis of Vessels in Eye: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Generalized Analysis of Vessels in Eye

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

GAVE

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

This challenge focuses on analyzing the vascular structure in color fundus photographs, specifically extracting retinal blood vessels and distinguishing between arteries and veins. Retinal blood vessel characteristics, such as caliber and structure, serve as important biomarkers for diagnosing and monitoring various medical conditions, including glaucoma, age-related macular degeneration, diabetic retinopathy, and hypertension. These biomarkers can be obtained through color fundus photography, a non-invasive and cost-effective imaging technique. Due to its affordability and ease of use, this technique has been widely adopted in clinical practice, research, and national screening programs.

To conduct a comprehensive analysis of the retinal vascular system, it is essential to first segment the blood vessels and then classify them as arteries or veins. The resulting artery-vein segmentation maps enable the quantification of diagnostically relevant features such as blood vessel width, diameter, and tortuosity. Accurate measurement of these features further facilitates the calculation of complex biomarkers, such as the arteriolar-to-venular diameter ratio.

Beyond blood vessel and artery-vein segmentation in color fundus photographs, this challenge introduces a novel task: the automatic measurement of the arteriovenous ratio. This measurement is closely linked to various cardiovascular conditions, including arteriosclerosis and hypertensive lesions, adding both depth to the challenge and significant implications for real-world medical applications. The core objective of this challenge is to achieve automated and precise blood vessel segmentation, artery-vein classification, and arteriovenous ratio measurement using color fundus photographs.

The challenge dataset consists of 150 color fundus photographs collected from different hospitals using various imaging devices, along with corresponding segmentation and arteriovenous ratio annotations. In the preliminary stage, 50 datasets with labels will be provided for model training, followed by the release of another 50 datasets

for validation. An online evaluation platform will be available, allowing teams to refine their models based on leaderboard rankings. In the final stage, the remaining 50 datasets will be released for model evaluation.

From a technical perspective, this challenge involves research on image segmentation in computer vision, a critical aspect of computer-aided clinical diagnosis. From a biomedical perspective, it aims to accurately extract the retinal vascular structure, contributing significantly to the understanding and identification of various diseases.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Color Fundus Photography, Vessel Segmentation, Artery/Vein Segmentation, Arteriovenous Ratio

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

The novelty of this challenge lies in several key aspects. First, precise segmentation of the vascular structure in color fundus photographs is not merely an objective in itself but a crucial foundation for further analysis. Once the blood vessels are accurately segmented, it enables highly precise measurements of critical parameters, such as vessel width, diameter, and tortuosity, with the arteriovenous ratio being the most significant. These parameters are essential not only for assessing the local condition of the retinal vascular system but also as important biomarkers for diagnosing and monitoring various systemic diseases.

Second, the dataset introduces a significant domain shift, encouraging participants to develop robust and generalized techniques. This aspect enhances the adaptability of the proposed methods to real-world clinical scenarios, increasing the practical value of the research outcomes.

From a data perspective, while relatively large datasets exist for blood vessel segmentation, such as FIVES, labeled images for artery-vein segmentation remain scarce. Additionally, no dedicated dataset currently exists for arteriovenous ratio measurement. To address this gap, we will release 150 annotated images, significantly enriching the available resources for artery-vein segmentation and providing a unique opportunity for arteriovenous ratio research. This comprehensive dataset will offer high-quality materials for model training and evaluation, ultimately improving the reliability and accuracy of research in this field.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

Our challenge encompasses three critical tasks that are deeply interconnected and hold significant clinical and research value. The first task focuses on retinal vessel segmentation, requiring participants to develop algorithms that can accurately identify and isolate blood vessels in color fundus images. Building on this, the second task involves artery/vein segmentation, where the goal is to classify the segmented vessels into arteries and veins based on their distinct characteristics, such as color, caliber, and branching patterns. This step is particularly challenging, as it demands a precise understanding of vascular morphology. The third and final task is the

automatic measurement of the arteriovenous ratio (AVR), a crucial biomarker for various diseases. Using the artery/vein segmentation results, algorithms must accurately calculate the ratio of arteriolar to venular diameter, which is essential for assessing conditions like diabetic retinopathy, hypertensive retinopathy, and even systemic diseases such as cardiovascular disorders and Alzheimer's disease. These tasks are not only valuable in clinical diagnosis but also serve as the foundation for AI-assisted diagnostic systems and large-scale public health screening programs. By automating the analysis of color fundus photographs, these techniques enable early disease detection and intervention, particularly in resource-limited regions where access to specialized medical care is scarce. Furthermore, they provide critical insights for research into retinal microcirculation, metabolic changes, and the biomechanical properties of the eye. Ultimately, the successful execution of these tasks has far-reaching implications, enhancing diagnostic accuracy, improving patient outcomes, and advancing the development of intelligent medical imaging solutions.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

OMIA12 – The 12th Ophthalmic Medical Image Analysis Workshop

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

Our challenge this year will be jointly held with another two challenges in the field of ophthalmic image analysis. The preliminary proposed titles are "Cataract Surgery Challenge" and "Domain adaptation for clinic-to-home OCT retinal layer segmentation (DOCTR) Challenge". During the event, an introduction to each challenge will be provided, and the challenge process will be reviewed. In addition, at least three teams from each challenge will share and discuss their solutions. Therefore, the three challenges will take half a day. It's worth noting that we plan to jointly organize a full-day event with OMIA12. For example, in the morning, there will be activities such as keynote speeches, paper sharing, and discussions at the workshop, while in the afternoon, the challenge activities will be held.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We anticipate that around 80 teams will sign up for the challenge, and over 800 person-times of result submissions will be received. Ultimately, we will choose 5 - 10 teams (approximately 10 - 30 participants) to proceed to the finals and attend the OMIA12 workshop in person.

Back in MICCAI 2018, we organized the 1st REFUGE challenge. During that event, a total of 334 participants registered, out of which 239 submitted results and took part in the challenge. Eventually, 12 teams, with approximately 45 participants in total, made it to the final at OMIA5.

In MICCAI 2019, we initiated the AGE challenge. There were 414 participants who registered for it, and 261 of them submitted results and got involved in the challenge. Subsequently, 8 teams, consisting of approximately 30

participants, were selected to participate in the final at OMIA6.

During MICCAI 2020, we organized the 2nd REFUGE challenge. An impressive 1547 participants registered for this challenge, and 961 of them submitted results and joined in. As a result, 22 teams, with around 60 participants in total, were able to participate in the final at OMIA7.

In MICCAI 2021, we organized the GAMMA contest. A total of 388 teams (nearly 1500 participants) registered for it. During the preliminary stage, 54 teams (almost 220 participants) submitted their results for the online set. Eventually, 10 teams (almost 40 participants) were picked to take part in the final at OMIA8.

In MICCAI 2022, we organized the GOALS challenge. More than 500 teams registered in total, and over 3000 person-times of result submissions were received. Finally, 15 teams (almost 60 participants) advanced from the preliminaries and participated in the final at OMIA9.

In MICCAI 2023, we organized the STAGE challenge. Over 150 teams registered in total, and more than 630 person-times of result submissions were received. Eventually, 7 teams (almost 20 participants) emerged from the preliminaries and participated in the final at OMIA-X.

In MICCAI 2024, we organized the STAGE2 challenge. More than 50 teams registered in total, and over 500 person-times of result submissions were received. Finally, 7 teams (almost 20 participants) made their way from the preliminaries and participated in the final at OMIA11.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

We will prepare a challenge review paper for IEEE transactions on medical imaging (TMI) or Medical Image Analysis (MIA). The review papers of REFUGE1 (2018), AGE (2019), PALM (2019), ADAM (2020), GAMMA (2021) have been published in MIA (DOI: 10.1016/j.media.2019.101570, DOI: 10.1016/j.media.2020.101798, and DOI: 10.1016/j.media.2023.102938), TMI (DOI: 10.1109/TMI.2022.3172773), and Sci.Data (DOI: 10.1038/s41597-024-02911-2). The review papers of GOALS (2022), STAGE1(2023), and STAGE2 (2024) have been or will be submitted to TMI or MIA.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

One projector and three microphones are needed.

A computing platform that can make the evaluation based on the results submitted by each team is needed. The specific ranking evaluation algorithm which needs to consider the results of both online and onsite sets will be provided by the organizer, and only a computer is required on site.

TASK 1: Retinal vessel segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

In the construction of the task for this generalized vessel analysis in eye challenge, the first task focuses on segmenting the vascular regions from color fundus photographs. The retinal blood vessels possess a rich variety of geometric features, including vessel diameter, branch angles, and branch lengths. These geometric features have significant implications for clinical and pathological representations and can provide crucial reference bases for the diagnosis of diseases such as hypertension, diabetes, and atherosclerosis.

In the field of ophthalmic clinical practice, ophthalmologists usually diagnose diseases related to blood vessel and vascular system lesions by referring to the status of retinal blood vessels. Common diseases that can lead to global blindness, such as diabetic retinopathy and diabetic maculopathy, all require careful observation and analysis of the retinal blood vessels for disease judgment and interpretation.

In the overall process of retinal blood vessel analysis, the step of retinal blood vessel segmentation undoubtedly occupies a crucial position. As the foundational step for subsequent in-depth analysis work, it plays a decisive role in ensuring the coherence and effectiveness of the entire analysis process.

From a technical perspective, this task falls within the scope of segmentation research in the fields of computer vision and artificial intelligence. In the development process of these fields, segmentation tasks demonstrate significant importance. With its outstanding ability to accurately distinguish different target objects in images, segmentation tasks have laid a solid foundation and provided indispensable key support for numerous application scenarios such as image understanding, object recognition, medical image diagnosis, and even autonomous driving.

From a biomedical perspective, retinal blood vessel segmentation also has undeniable value. On the one hand, it lays a solid foundation for exploring the innovative direction of diagnosing systemic vascular system lesions through ocular features, which helps to expand the approaches and horizons of medical diagnosis. On the other hand, in the specific practice of ophthalmic disease diagnosis and treatment, this technology can provide medical workers with objective and accurate structural information of ocular organs, assisting them in making more scientific and accurate diagnostic decisions and providing a strong basis for formulating reasonable and effective treatment plans later.

In conclusion, setting retinal blood vessel segmentation as the first task of this challenge is not only an inevitable choice in line with the development trend of computer vision and artificial intelligence technologies but also meets the practical needs of the biomedical field in disease diagnosis and research, demonstrating a high degree of scientificity and rationality.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Vessel segmentation, color fundus photography

ORGANIZATION**Organizers**

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Huihui Fang, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore.

Yanwu Xu, South China University of Technology, Guangzhou, China.

Weihua Yang, Shenzhen Eye Hospital, Shenzhen, China.

Hrvoje Bogunović, Medical University of Vienna, Austria.

Huazhu Fu, Agency for Science, Technology and Research, Singapore.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Huihui Fang (fanghuihuibit@163.com)

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

OMIA12 – The 12th Ophthalmic Medical Image Analysis Workshop

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

aistudio.baidu.com

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

To Be Determined.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top 3 teams in the whole challenge will receive the prize as in previous years. The bonus pool is not less than 4000 USD.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Submissions will be scored and ranked based on evaluation metrics. All scores and rankings will be displayed on a publicly available leaderboard on the challenge website. Teams that perform well in the preliminaries will be invited to the finals and the OMIA workshop. All finalist teams are required to submit technical reports and codes, which are authorized for publication. It is worth noting that the teams from enterprises can only publish technical reports if they cannot disclose the code due to confidentiality factors.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The top teams in the final will be invited, with a maximum of 2 authors per team, to contribute to a joint journal paper(s) describing and summarizing the methods used and results found in this challenge. The paper will be submitted to a high-impact journal in the field. The participating teams could publish their own methods and results separately.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The algorithm output will be requested to be sent to the AI Studio platform and then be automatically evaluated. And, after the preliminary stage, the organizer will collect the codes and results of the top 20-30 teams for

verification, and the top 5-15 teams who are willing to submit and have valid codes will enter the final. (The number of teams collecting materials and the number of teams in the final will be adjusted according to the actual number of participants). Submission instructions will be available on the AI Studio platform's challenge page.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

During the preliminary, each team can submit at most 3 times per day. Once the quota of submission is exhausted, it will not be able to submit within the same day; the score for each submission will be displayed on the team's submission page, but only the best historical result will be displayed on the leaderboard page. (if the new submission results are better than the previous submission results, the performance of the participant in the leaderboard will be automatically updated and covered. On the other hand, the rankings remain the same.) During the finals, each team has only one chance to submit its results.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

2025/06/01 Start the challenge registration

2025/07/01 Release training dataset for download

2024/07/04 Release preliminary dataset for download and open the entry of preliminary leaderboard evaluation

2025/08/17 Close the entrance of the preliminary leaderboard, and the top 30 teams submit materials for review

2025/08/25 Deadline for submission of review materials

2025/09/01 Determine teams for the finals

2025/09/05 Release the encrypted final dataset to the final teams

2025/09/06 Release the password of the final dataset and submit the final result within a limited time

2025/09/23or27 Announce the ranking and award of the final in MICCAI 2025 OMIA Workshop

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The original data employed in this challenge proposal received approval from the Institutional Review Board of Shenzhen Eye Hospital, China, on February 6, 2024. The approval number is 2024KYPJ013.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

We will provide evaluation code on Github.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

After the challenge, we will release the finalist teams' technical reports and codes on the challenge website. It is worth noting that enterprise teams that cannot disclose code due to confidentiality factors will only release technical reports.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The prize will be sponsored by the organizers' institute, the members of the institute are not allowed to list in the leaderboard in this challenge. The challenge dataset (original images and labels) will be provided by Shenzhen Eye Hospital, whose members are not allowed to list in the leaderboard in this challenge. No one else will have access to the test case labels except the challenge organizers.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up

- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Decision support,Diagnosis,Screening

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

People who visit the eye hospital or ophthalmology department in the general hospital.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

People who visit the eye hospital or ophthalmology department in the general hospital.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Color fundus photography(CFP), CFP is currently the most economical, non-invasive imaging modality for inspecting the retina.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

None

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

None

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The data are color fundus photographs collected from the subjects' eyes.

The research content is the retinal vessels in the color fundus photographs.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The Retinal vessels are the algorithm target, i.e., the participating algorithms will be designed to focus on them for segmentation.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy

DATA SETS**Data source(s)**

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The collection equipment for color fundus images includes Topcon NW400, Canon CR-2 AF, Kowa VX-10i, Zeiss VIUCAM200 and other fundus cameras commonly used in eye hospitals.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

(1) Instruct the patient to sit in front of the device relaxed, place the jaw on the jaw bracket, and press the forehead forward close to the device. Adjust the height of the jaw bracket so that the height of the patient's outer canthal is at the level of the eye position marker, and instruct the patient to gaze at the fixed cursor inside the lens of the device.

(2) Aim the scanning head at the center of the patient's pupil, and then gradually advance until a clear image appears on the display screen, and adjust the image until it is clear (including the edge).

(3) Automatic focusing or manual focusing can be selected to adjust the target diopter, iris focusing, pupil position and color fundus image centering.

(4) Adjust the scope of the fundus covered by the scanning frame to be consistent with the site required for clinical examination. The center of the field of view of the photographs were either placed in the optic disc, the macula, or the midpoint of the optic disc and macula.

(5) Ensure that the scanned retina light band is clear and placed in the middle of the display screen observation window, with high signal intensity and uniform brightness.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Shenzhen Eye Hospital, China

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Ophthalmologists and technicians operate color fundus photographs with at least 5 years of collecting experience.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and test cases both represent a color fundus image of a human eye. Training and test cases both have segmentation annotation of the retinal vessels.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

A total of 150 color fundus images are available. The dataset is split into 3 subsets for training (50), preliminary validation (50), and final test (50).

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

We investigated datasets related to retinal vessel segmentation and arteriovenous segmentation in color fundus images. While the FIVES dataset contains 800 annotated fundus images for vascular segmentation, publicly available datasets that include both vascular and arteriovenous segmentation annotations remain limited. Notable examples include the RAVIR dataset, the arteriovenous annotation versions of the DRIVE and HRF datasets, and the VICAVR dataset, which contain only 42, 40, 30, and 58 annotated cases, respectively. Given these limitations, we have structured our challenge dataset by allocating 50 samples each to the training set, the validation set (which also serves as the preliminary test set), and the final test set.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Since this challenge primarily focuses on the development of segmentation and measurement methods, the disease status of the cases has not been specifically accounted for at this stage. All published data are retrospective clinical outpatient records, encompassing a diverse range of disease conditions. Once the data collation is complete, we will provide more detailed information on the challenge website, including age distribution, disease prevalence, and other relevant statistics.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All the data released in this challenge are new and have never been made public before.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The data annotation for this challenge was mainly completed manually by doctors. We simultaneously collected fluorescein fundus angiography (FFA) images with filled arteries and those with both arteries and veins filled for each case. The purpose was to use these two FFA images to guide the differentiation and annotation of arteries and veins in the fundus blood vessels.

The manual annotation team consisted of three primary annotating doctors and one quality control doctor with higher seniority.

The annotating doctors first observed the FFA images with filled arteries, identified the arterial branches in the color fundus photographs, and then used the Labelme tool to outline the edges of the targets. Subsequently, they used the FFA images with both arteries and veins filled to identify the remaining vein branches in the color fundus photographs and again used the Labelme tool to outline the edges of the targets. For the overlapping areas of

arteries and veins, they were annotated separately.

The vessel segmentation label for Task 1 will provide a union mask of arteries, veins, and overlapping areas.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

LabelMe is a very simple and practical image annotation software. For the annotation of our segmentation tasks, annotators need to accurately cover the boundaries of the targets with polylines. If the drawn polylines do not cover certain parts of the boundaries, annotators can modify the original polylines by adding turning points to make them closer to the real boundaries.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Three experienced ophthalmologists and one senior ophthalmologist from Shenzhen Eye Hospital are invited to annotate the cases (training, validation and test cases). The three experienced ophthalmologists have an average of 8 years of experience in the field, with individual experience ranging from 5 to 10 years. The senior ophthalmologist has over 15 years of experience. First, for the primary annotation, the experienced ophthalmologist independently reviewed and delineated the target boundaries in all the images, without having access to any patient information or knowledge of disease prevalence in the data.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We will use the majority voting method to merge the results marked by the three primary annotators, and then the results will be checked by the qualified quality control ophthalmologist, who will correct the data marked with deviations.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Quality control and anonymization: only qualified images (Fundus structures are clear, which can be used for clinical diagnosis) are selected for manual annotation and to provide to the participating teams. And the personal information is removed.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Inter-/ intra-observer variability.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

For Task 1, we chose to use the Dice Similarity Coefficient, a commonly used metric for evaluating segmentation tasks. Additionally, to assess the segmentation accuracy along the blood vessel boundaries, we selected the 95% Hausdorff Distance as an evaluation metric. Furthermore, for the segmentation of tubular structures like blood vessels, we also used the Centerline Dice (cIDice) index to evaluate topological connectivity.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

In Task 1 of retinal vessel segmentation, the Dice Similarity Coefficient is selected as it effectively measures the overlap between the predicted and ground-truth masks. The 95% Hausdorff Distance is used to assess boundary accuracy, which is crucial for detecting subtle boundary changes in early-stage eye diseases such as hypertensive retinopathy. The Centerline Dice (cIDice) index is applied to tubular blood vessel structures to evaluate topological connectivity, which is vital for understanding blood flow patterns in the retinal microcirculation. Together, these metrics provide a comprehensive evaluation of various aspects of retinal vessel segmentation, which are essential for diagnosing and understanding both ophthalmic and systemic diseases related to the retinal vascular system.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

When designing the score calculation, we set the proportions of the Dice score, HD95 score, and cIDice score to be 0.4, 0.3, and 0.3 respectively.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

We do not allow submissions with missing results. In the submission instructions, we will clearly state that each test case must have a corresponding test result. Otherwise, the evaluation platform will return an error message to remind the participants to check the integrity of their submitted results.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The score for retinal vessel segmentation is calculated as $\text{Score_task1} = 0.4 \cdot \text{DSC} + 0.3 \cdot (\lambda \cdot (1 / (\text{HD95} + 1))) + 0.3 \cdot \text{cIDice}$. DSC and cIDice are in the range of 0 - 100 (in percentage). Lambda controls the score range of HD95 which ranges from 0 to infinity. In previous studies, HD95 was in 70 - 200, so we tentatively set lambda as 5000. Lambda will be adjusted according to dataset performance to make the HD95 score range from 0 to 100.

In the challenge, the final score of this task will be considered in a combination of the preliminary round and the final round. The final score is

$\text{Score_task1}(\text{total}) = 0.3 \cdot \text{Score_task1}(\text{preliminary round}) + 0.7 \cdot \text{Score_task1}(\text{final round})$.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Missing data not allowed (incomplete submissions not evaluated).

The statistical significance of the differences in performance of the top-ranked teams was assessed by means of Wilcoxon signed-rank tests ($= 0.05$).

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test is a non-parametric statistical hypothesis test used either to test the location of a set of samples or to compare the locations of two populations using a set of matched samples.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

In the challenge review paper, we will have further analysis of the above four points, including combining algorithms via ensembling, inter-algorithm variability, common problems/biases of the submitted methods, and ranking variability.

TASK 2: Artery/vein segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Task 2 focuses on segmenting arteries and veins from color fundus photographs. The retinal artery, as a vascular channel that transports blood rich in oxygen and nutrients from the heart to the retina and surrounding ocular tissues, has a relatively thin diameter, a thick vessel wall, a fast blood flow velocity, high pressure, and a bright red color. Moreover, its branches form a tree-like structure to cover a wide area of the retina. On the other hand, the retinal vein is mainly responsible for transporting blood with reduced oxygen content and carrying metabolic wastes back to the heart. Its diameter is slightly thicker than that of the artery in the same area, with a thinner vessel wall, a slow blood flow velocity, low pressure, and a dark red color. Its branches are distributed along the gaps between the arterial branches, forming a network for collecting blood. Accurately distinguishing between the retinal artery and vein is of crucial significance for understanding the physiological mechanism of ocular blood circulation as well as disease diagnosis and monitoring.

For example, many ophthalmic diseases and systemic diseases can cause characteristic changes in the retinal arteries and veins in the early stage. In diabetic retinopathy, for instance, abnormalities may occur at the intersections of arteries and veins in the early stage, such as local dilation of veins and increased compression of veins by arteries. Around the optic nerve head of glaucoma patients, the arteries may become thinner and the blood perfusion may decrease. Through accurate segmentation of the retinal arteries and veins, these subtle changes can be detected in a timely manner, providing an important basis for the early diagnosis of diseases. In addition, the status of retinal arteries and veins is also related to many non-ophthalmic diseases. Systemic diseases such as hypertension and arteriosclerosis can lead to disorders in the diameter ratio of retinal arteries and veins and hardening changes in the vessel walls. By segmenting the retinal arteries and veins and analyzing their characteristics, doctors can comprehensively judge whether patients have multiple potential diseases, thereby improving the comprehensiveness and accuracy of diagnosis.

Therefore, in this challenge, we have set it as a separate research task. From a technical perspective, this task belongs to the research on segmentation and classification, which is a very basic technical research area in the fields of computer vision and artificial intelligence. From a biomedical perspective, the research on retinal artery and vein segmentation can lay a foundation for doctors to explore the commonalities and differences of different diseases in the retinal arteries and veins, and provide theoretical support for the precise diagnosis and individualized treatment of diseases.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Artery/vein segmentation, color fundus photography

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Huihui Fang, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore.

Yanwu Xu, South China University of Technology, Guangzhou, China.

Weihua Yang, Shenzhen Eye Hospital, Shenzhen, China.

Hrvoje Bogunović, Medical University of Vienna, Austria.

Huazhu Fu, Agency for Science, Technology and Research, Singapore.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Huihui Fang (fanghuihui@163.com)

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

OMIA12 – The 12th Ophthalmic Medical Image Analysis Workshop

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

aistudio.baidu.com

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

To Be Determined.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top 3 teams in the whole challenge will receive the prize as in previous years. The bonus pool is not less than 4000 USD.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Submissions will be scored and ranked based on evaluation metrics. All scores and rankings will be displayed on a publicly available leaderboard on the challenge website. Teams that perform well in the preliminaries will be invited to the finals and the OMIA workshop. All finalist teams are required to submit technical reports and codes, which are authorized for publication. It is worth noting that the teams from enterprises can only publish technical reports if they cannot disclose the code due to confidentiality factors.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The top teams in the final will be invited, with a maximum of 2 authors per team, to contribute to a joint journal paper(s) describing and summarizing the methods used and results found in this challenge. The paper will be submitted to a high-impact journal in the field. The participating teams could publish their own methods and results separately.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The algorithm output will be requested to be sent to the AI Studio platform and then be automatically evaluated. And, after the preliminary stage, the organizer will collect the codes and results of the top 20-30 teams for verification, and the top 5-15 teams who are willing to submit and have valid codes will enter the final. (The number of teams collecting materials and the number of teams in the final will be adjusted according to the actual number of participants). Submission instructions will be available on the AI Studio platform's challenge page.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

During the preliminary, each team can submit at most 3 times per day. Once the quota of submission is exhausted, it will not be able to submit within the same day; the score for each submission will be displayed on the team's submission page, but only the best historical result will be displayed on the leaderboard page. (if the new submission results are better than the previous submission results, the performance of the participant in the leaderboard will be automatically updated and covered. On the other hand, the rankings remain the same.) During the finals, each team has only one chance to submit its results.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

2025/06/01 Start the challenge registration

2025/07/01 Release training dataset for download

2024/07/04 Release preliminary dataset for download and open the entry of preliminary leaderboard evaluation

2025/08/17 Close the entrance of the preliminary leaderboard, and the top 30 teams submit materials for review

2025/08/25 Deadline for submission of review materials

2025/09/01 Determine teams for the finals

2025/09/05 Release the encrypted final dataset to the final teams

2025/09/06 Release the password of the final dataset and submit the final result within a limited time

2025/09/23or27 Announce the ranking and award of the final in MICCAI 2025 OMIA Workshop

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The original data employed in this challenge proposal received approval from the Institutional Review Board of Shenzhen Eye Hospital, China, on February 6, 2024. The approval number is 2024KYPJ013.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)

- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

We will provide evaluation code on Github.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

After the challenge, we will release the finalist teams' technical reports and codes on the challenge website. It is worth noting that enterprise teams that cannot disclose code due to confidentiality factors will only release technical reports.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The prize will be sponsored by the organizers' institute, the members of the institute are not allowed to list in the leaderboard in this challenge. The challenge dataset (original images and labels) will be provided by Shenzhen Eye Hospital, whose members are not allowed to list in the leaderboard in this challenge. No one else will have access to the test case labels except the challenge organizers.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Decision support,Diagnosis,Screening

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation,Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

People who visit the eye hospital or ophthalmology department in the general hospital.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

People who visit the eye hospital or ophthalmology department in the general hospital.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Color fundus photography(CFP), CFP is currently the most economical, non-invasive imaging modality for inspecting the retina.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

None

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

None

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The data are color fundus photographs collected from the subjects' eyes.

The research content is the retinal artery and vein in the color fundus photographs.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The Retinal artery and vein are the algorithm target, i.e., the participating algorithms will be designed to focus on them for segmentation.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The collection equipment for color fundus images includes Topcon NW400, Canon CR-2 AF, Kowa VX-10i, Zeiss VIUCAM200 and other fundus cameras commonly used in eye hospitals.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

(1) Instruct the patient to sit in front of the device relaxed, place the jaw on the jaw bracket, and press the forehead forward close to the device. Adjust the height of the jaw bracket so that the height of the patient's outer canthal is at the level of the eye position marker, and instruct the patient to gaze at the fixed cursor inside the

lens of the device.

(2) Aim the scanning head at the center of the patient's pupil, and then gradually advance until a clear image appears on the display screen, and adjust the image until it is clear (including the edge).

(3) Automatic focusing or manual focusing can be selected to adjust the target diopter, iris focusing, pupil position and color fundus image centering.

(4) Adjust the scope of the fundus covered by the scanning frame to be consistent with the site required for clinical examination. The center of the field of view of the photographs were either placed in the optic disc, the macula, or the midpoint of the optic disc and macula.

(5) Ensure that the scanned retina light band is clear and placed in the middle of the display screen observation window, with high signal intensity and uniform brightness.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Shenzhen Eye Hospital, China

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Ophthalmologists and technicians operate color fundus photographs with at least 5 years of collecting experience.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and test cases both represent a color fundus image of a human eye. Training and test cases both have segmentation annotation of the retinal artery and vein.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

A total of 150 color fundus images are available. The dataset is split into 3 subsets for training (50), preliminary validation (50), and final test (50).

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

We investigated datasets related to retinal vessel segmentation and arteriovenous segmentation in color fundus images. While the FIVES dataset contains 800 annotated fundus images for vascular segmentation, publicly available datasets that include both vascular and arteriovenous segmentation annotations remain limited. Notable examples include the RAVIR dataset, the arteriovenous annotation versions of the DRIVE and HRF

datasets, and the VICAVR dataset, which contain only 42, 40, 30, and 58 annotated cases, respectively. Given these limitations, we have structured our challenge dataset by allocating 50 samples each to the training set, the validation set (which also serves as the preliminary test set), and the final test set.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Since this challenge primarily focuses on the development of segmentation and measurement methods, the disease status of the cases has not been specifically accounted for at this stage. All published data are retrospective clinical outpatient records, encompassing a diverse range of disease conditions. Once the data collation is complete, we will provide more detailed information on the challenge website, including age distribution, disease prevalence, and other relevant statistics.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All the data released in this challenge are new and have never been made public before.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The data annotation for this challenge was mainly completed manually by doctors. We simultaneously collected fluorescein fundus angiography (FFA) images with filled arteries and those with both arteries and veins filled for each case. The purpose was to use these two FFA images to guide the differentiation and annotation of arteries and veins in the fundus blood vessels.

The manual annotation team consisted of three primary annotating doctors and one quality control doctor with higher seniority.

The annotating doctors first observed the FFA images with filled arteries, identified the arterial branches in the color fundus photographs, and then used the Labelme tool to outline the edges of the targets. Subsequently, they used the FFA images with both arteries and veins filled to identify the remaining vein branches in the color fundus photographs and again used the Labelme tool to outline the edges of the targets. For the overlapping areas of arteries and veins, they were annotated separately.

The artery-vein segmentation label for Task 2 will provide masks of arteries, veins, and overlapping areas with different pixel values.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

LabelMe is a very simple and practical image annotation software. For the annotation of our segmentation tasks, annotators need to accurately cover the boundaries of the targets with polylines. If the drawn polylines do not cover certain parts of the boundaries, annotators can modify the original polylines by adding turning points to make them closer to the real boundaries.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Three experienced ophthalmologists and one senior ophthalmologist from Shenzhen Eye Hospital are invited to annotate the cases (training, validation and test cases). The three experienced ophthalmologists have an average of 8 years of experience in the field, with individual experience ranging from 5 to 10 years. The senior ophthalmologist has over 15 years of experience. First, for the primary annotation, the experienced ophthalmologist independently reviewed and delineated the target boundaries in all the images, without having access to any patient information or knowledge of disease prevalence in the data.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

We will use the majority voting method to merge the results marked by the three primary annotators, and then the results will be checked by the qualified quality control ophthalmologist, who will correct the data marked with deviations.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Quality control and anonymization: only qualified images (Fundus structures are clear, which can be used for clinical diagnosis) are selected for manual annotation and to provide to the participating teams. And the personal information is removed.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Inter-/ intra-observer variability.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

For Task 2, we also choose to use the Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), which is commonly used in the evaluation of segmentation tasks, as well as three evaluation metrics from the perspective of different blood vessel attribute

classification, namely Sensitivity (Sen), Specificity (Spec), and Accuracy (Acc).

Additionally, we assessed the topological connectivity of A/V segmentation maps using infeasible (INF) and correct (COR) path percentages.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Firstly, the Dice Similarity Coefficient is usually employed in the evaluation of medical segmentation.

Secondly, we utilize classification evaluation metrics to judge the discriminative ability of the participating teams' models regarding blood vessel attributes.

For Task 2, with reference to recent studies, we evaluate the topological connectivity of artery and vein branches, which can help us gain a better understanding of the practical capabilities of the participating algorithms.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

When designing the score calculation, we set the proportions of the segmentation evaluation metrics, the classification evaluation metrics, and the topological connectivity evaluation metrics in the total score to 0.3, 0.3, and 0.4 respectively. Among the classification evaluation metrics, the proportions of Sensitivity (Sen), Specificity (Spec), and Accuracy (Acc) are designed to be 0.3, 0.3, and 0.4 respectively. Among the topological connectivity evaluation metrics, the proportions of "infeasible (INF)" and "correct (COR)" are both set to 0.5.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

We do not allow submissions with missing results. In the submission instructions, we will clearly state that each test case must have a corresponding test result. Otherwise, the evaluation platform will return an error message to remind the participants to check the integrity of their submitted results.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The score calculation for the retinal artery and vein segmentation is

$Score_task2 = 0.3*(0.3*Sen+0.3*Spec+0.4*Acc)+0.3*DSC+0.4*(0.5*Cor+0.5*(\lambda*(1/(INF+1))))$. Lambda controls the score range of INF to be less than 0-100.

In the challenge, the final score of this task will be considered in a combination of the preliminary round and the final round. The final score is

$Score_task2(total)=0.3*Score_task2 (preliminary round)+0.7*Score_task2(final round)$.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Missing data not allowed (incomplete submissions not evaluated).

The statistical significance of the differences in performance of the top-ranked teams was assessed by means of Wilcoxon signed-rank tests ($= 0.05$).

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test is a non-parametric statistical hypothesis test used either to test the location of a set of samples or to compare the locations of two populations using a set of matched samples.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

In the challenge review paper, we will have further analysis of the above four points, including combining algorithms via ensembling, inter-algorithm variability, common problems/biases of the submitted methods, and ranking variability.

TASK 3: Arteriovenous ratio automatic measurement

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Task 3 focuses on the automatic measurement of the arteriovenous ratio (AVR) in color fundus photographs. As a crucial biomarker, the AVR reflects the relative diameters of arterioles and venules in the retinal vascular network. Beyond serving as an indicator of normal ocular blood circulation, it is a sensitive marker for detecting various diseases.

In clinical practice, significant changes in the AVR are closely linked to a range of ophthalmic and systemic conditions. For instance, in hypertensive retinopathy, an elevated AVR often signals increased systemic blood pressure, leading to alterations in retinal vessel diameters. Similarly, in arteriosclerosis, the hardening and narrowing of arterial walls can result in abnormal fluctuations in the AVR. By enabling accurate and automated AVR measurement, this task facilitates early disease detection, allowing for timely intervention and treatment.

From a technical standpoint, this task lies at the intersection of image processing, computer vision, and machine learning. Given the segmented arteries and veins from Task 2, advanced algorithms must be developed to precisely measure vessel diameters and compute the AVR. This requires sophisticated techniques in edge detection, object quantification, and data analysis to ensure high precision and robustness.

In biomedical research, automated AVR measurement provides a valuable tool for investigating the relationship between retinal vascular changes and disease mechanisms. It enables researchers to better understand how systemic diseases impact retinal microcirculation, contributing to the development of novel diagnostic methods and therapeutic strategies.

In summary, the automatic measurement of the AVR is not only of great significance for clinical diagnosis and disease monitoring but also represents a cutting-edge research area in medical technology. Its potential to enhance disease detection, improve patient outcomes, and advance scientific understanding underscores its high value in both medical practice and research.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Arteriovenous ratio, automatic measurement

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Huihui Fang, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore.

Yanwu Xu, South China University of Technology, Guangzhou, China.

Weihua Yang, Shenzhen Eye Hospital, Shenzhen, China.

Hrvoje Bogunović, Medical University of Vienna, Austria.

Huazhu Fu, Agency for Science, Technology and Research, Singapore.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Huihui Fang (fanghuihuibit@163.com)

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

OMIA12 – The 12th Ophthalmic Medical Image Analysis Workshop

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

aistudio.baidu.com

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

To Be Determined.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully interactive

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top 3 teams in the whole challenge will receive the prize as in previous years. The bonus pool is not less than 4000 USD.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Submissions will be scored and ranked based on evaluation metrics. All scores and rankings will be displayed on a publicly available leaderboard on the challenge website. Teams that perform well in the preliminaries will be invited to the finals and the OMIA workshop. All finalist teams are required to submit technical reports and codes, which are authorized for publication. It is worth noting that the teams from enterprises can only publish technical reports if they cannot disclose the code due to confidentiality factors.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The top teams in the final will be invited, with a maximum of 2 authors per team, to contribute to a joint journal paper(s) describing and summarizing the methods used and results found in this challenge. The paper will be submitted to a high-impact journal in the field. The participating teams could publish their own methods and results separately.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The algorithm output will be requested to be sent to the AI Studio platform and then be automatically evaluated. And, after the preliminary stage, the organizer will collect the codes and results of the top 20-30 teams for verification, and the top 5-15 teams who are willing to submit and have valid codes will enter the final. (The number of teams collecting materials and the number of teams in the final will be adjusted according to the actual number of participants). Submission instructions will be available on the AI Studio platform's challenge page.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

During the preliminary, each team can submit at most 3 times per day. Once the quota of submission is exhausted, it will not be able to submit within the same day; the score for each submission will be displayed on the team's submission page, but only the best historical result will be displayed on the leaderboard page. (if the

new submission results are better than the previous submission results, the performance of the participant in the leaderboard will be automatically updated and covered. On the other hand, the rankings remain the same.) During the finals, each team has only one chance to submit its results.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

2025/06/01 Start the challenge registration

2025/07/01 Release training dataset for download

2024/07/04 Release preliminary dataset for download and open the entry of preliminary leaderboard evaluation

2025/08/17 Close the entrance of the preliminary leaderboard, and the top 30 teams submit materials for review

2025/08/25 Deadline for submission of review materials

2025/09/01 Determine teams for the finals

2025/09/05 Release the encrypted final dataset to the final teams

2025/09/06 Release the password of the final dataset and submit the final result within a limited time

2025/09/23or27 Announce the ranking and award of the final in MICCAI 2025 OMIA Workshop

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The original data employed in this challenge proposal received approval from the Institutional Review Board of Shenzhen Eye Hospital, China, on February 6, 2024. The approval number is 2024KYPJ013.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

We will provide evaluation code on Github.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

After the challenge, we will release the finalist teams' technical reports and codes on the challenge website. It is worth noting that enterprise teams that cannot disclose code due to confidentiality factors will only release technical reports.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The prize will be sponsored by the organizers' institute, the members of the institute are not allowed to list in the leaderboard in this challenge. The challenge dataset (original images and labels) will be provided by Shenzhen Eye Hospital, whose members are not allowed to list in the leaderboard in this challenge. No one else will have access to the test case labels except the challenge organizers.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Decision support,Diagnosis,Screening

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Regression

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

People who visit the eye hospital or ophthalmology department in the general hospital.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

People who visit the eye hospital or ophthalmology department in the general hospital.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Color fundus photography(CFP), CFP is currently the most economical, non-invasive imaging modality for inspecting the retina.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

None

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

None

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The data are color fundus photographs collected from the subjects' eyes.

The research content is the ratio of retinal arteriovenous diameters in color fundus photographs.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The retinal artery and vein diameters and their ratios are the target of the algorithm, i.e. the participating algorithm will measure and calculate them.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The collection equipment for color fundus images includes Topcon NW400, Canon CR-2 AF, Kowa VX-10i, Zeiss VIUCAM200 and other fundus cameras commonly used in eye hospitals.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

(1) Instruct the patient to sit in front of the device relaxed, place the jaw on the jaw bracket, and press the forehead forward close to the device. Adjust the height of the jaw bracket so that the height of the patient's outer canthal is at the level of the eye position marker, and instruct the patient to gaze at the fixed cursor inside the lens of the device.

- (2) Aim the scanning head at the center of the patient's pupil, and then gradually advance until a clear image appears on the display screen, and adjust the image until it is clear (including the edge).
- (3) Automatic focusing or manual focusing can be selected to adjust the target diopter, iris focusing, pupil position and color fundus image centering.
- (4) Adjust the scope of the fundus covered by the scanning frame to be consistent with the site required for clinical examination. The center of the field of view of the photographs were either placed in the optic disc, the macula, or the midpoint of the optic disc and macula.
- (5) Ensure that the scanned retina light band is clear and placed in the middle of the display screen observation window, with high signal intensity and uniform brightness.
- c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Shenzhen Eye Hospital, China

- d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Ophthalmologists and technicians operate color fundus photographs with at least 5 years of collecting experience.

Training and test case characteristics

- a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and test cases both represent a color fundus image of a human eye. Training and test cases both have labels with the arteriovenous ratio of 4 key positions.

- b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

A total of 150 color fundus images are available. The dataset is split into 3 subsets for training (50), preliminary validation (50), and final test (50).

- c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

We investigated datasets related to retinal vessel segmentation and arteriovenous segmentation in color fundus images. While the FIVES dataset contains 800 annotated fundus images for vascular segmentation, publicly available datasets that include both vascular and arteriovenous segmentation annotations remain limited. Notable examples include the RAVIR dataset, the arteriovenous annotation versions of the DRIVE and HRF

datasets, and the VICAVR dataset, which contain only 42, 40, 30, and 58 annotated cases, respectively. Given these limitations, we have structured our challenge dataset by allocating 50 samples each to the training set, the validation set (which also serves as the preliminary test set), and the final test set.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Since this challenge primarily focuses on the development of segmentation and measurement methods, the disease status of the cases has not been specifically accounted for at this stage. All published data are retrospective clinical outpatient records, encompassing a diverse range of disease conditions. Once the data collation is complete, we will provide more detailed information on the challenge website, including age distribution, disease prevalence, and other relevant statistics.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All the data released in this challenge are new and have never been made public before.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The annotations for Task 3 were primarily completed manually by a team of ophthalmologists. The labeling team comprised three junior ophthalmologists and one senior ophthalmologist.

To establish the gold standard, the ophthalmologists first manually identified and classified the retinal arteries and veins in the marginal area of the optic disc. They then selected the four pairs of arteries and veins with the largest diameters and measured their respective diameters. Finally, the arteriovenous diameter ratios for these four groups were calculated to serve as the reference standard.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

LabelMe is a simple yet effective image annotation tool. For the annotation of the arteriovenous diameter ratio task, labeling requires only a mouse click on the vascular boundary points at the edge of the optic disc. The software automatically records the coordinates of these points, after which the vessel diameters are computed using a distance calculation formula. Finally, the arteriovenous diameter ratio is derived based on these measurements.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Three experienced ophthalmologists and one senior ophthalmologist from Shenzhen Eye Hospital are invited to annotate the cases (training, validation and test cases). The three experienced ophthalmologists have an average of 8 years of experience in the field, with individual experience ranging from 5 to 10 years. The senior

ophthalmologist has over 15 years of experience. First, for the primary annotation, the experienced ophthalmologist independently reviewed and delineated the target boundaries in all the images, without having access to any patient information or knowledge of disease prevalence in the data.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

A senior ophthalmologist will manually review the vascular boundary points selected by the three primary annotators. The ophthalmologist will first ensure that the branches of the arteries and veins marked for calculation are consistent. If discrepancies are found, the incorrect boundary points will be removed. Next, the coordinates of the remaining valid boundary points will be averaged. Finally, the arteriovenous diameters will be measured based on the determined boundary points, and the arteriovenous diameter ratio will be calculated.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Quality control and anonymization: only qualified images (Fundus structures are clear, which can be used for clinical diagnosis) are selected for manual annotation and to provide to the participating teams. And the personal information is removed.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Inter-/ intra-observer variability.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

In Task 3, we selected Mean Absolute Error (MAE), a commonly used metric for evaluating numerical tasks. Additionally, we chose Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error (SMAPE) to calculate the difference between the predicted value and the target value.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

For this regression task, the MAE and SMAPE metrics will be used. Compared to the MAE commonly used for regression tasks, SMAPE are bound, with the lower bound of 0% implying a perfect fit, and the upper bound of

200%. It is friendlier for the score calculation in the challenge and is more reflective of the degree of error. SMAPE is progressively gaining momentum in biomedical applications due to its interesting properties.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

When designing the score calculation, we set the ratio of MAE score and SMAPE score to 0.5 and 0.5, respectively

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

We do not allow submissions with missing results. In the submission instructions, we will clearly state that each test case must have a corresponding test result. Otherwise, the evaluation platform will return an error message to remind the participants to check the integrity of their submitted results.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The score calculation for the automatic measurement of the arteriovenous ratio is as follows: $\text{Score_task3} = 0.5 * (\lambda_1 * (1 / (\text{MAE} + 1))) + 0.5 * (\lambda_2 * (1 / (\text{SMAPE} + 1)))$. Here, λ_1 and λ_2 are parameters that regulate the score within the range of 0 - 100.

In this challenge, the final score for this task is determined by combining the scores from the preliminary and final rounds. Specifically, the total score is calculated as $\text{Score_task3}(\text{total}) = 0.3 * \text{Score_task3}(\text{preliminary round}) + 0.7 * \text{Score_task3}(\text{final round})$.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Missing data not allowed (incomplete submissions not evaluated).

The statistical significance of the differences in performance of the top-ranked teams was assessed by means of Wilcoxon signed-rank tests (= 0.05).

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test is a non-parametric statistical hypothesis test used either to test the location of a set of samples or to compare the locations of two populations using a set of matched samples.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,

- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

In the challenge review paper, we will have further analysis of the above four points, including combining algorithms via ensembling, inter-algorithm variability, common problems/biases of the submitted methods, and ranking variability.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

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Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

None.